

Ion-exchange Behaviour of Stannic Tungstophosphate towards Bivalent Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 19 September 1984, revised 16 August 1985, accepted 29 October 1985

Sn^{IV} tungstophosphate (Sn-W-P) was prepared by adding 0.1 M Sn^{IV} chloride solution to 0.1 M tungstophosphoric acid solution in different volume ratios. The dried gel of Sn-W-P was refluxed in 6 M phosphoric acid for 100 h before breaking down into small granules. Its ion-exchange capacity, chemical composition (Sn-W-P, 2 : 1 : 3.2), chemical dissolution, pH titration, heat treatment, ir spectra and distribution coefficients for 11 bivalent metal ions in various media have been studied. The quantitative separation of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}-Cu^{II} were also achieved on its columns.

THE present considerable status of the synthetic inorganic ion-exchange materials is due to their growing application potentiality in energy resources recovery, pollution abatement and in achieving metal ion separation of analytical scope.

The insoluble salts of hetero-polyacids with polyvalent metals are preferred to other ion-exchangers as they exhibit selective ion-exchange behaviour. Therefore, now-a-days the investigation of these salts has become a field of interest. Besides the sizable studies on simple salts, Qureshi *et al.* have published their findings on crystalline Sn^{IV}-vanadophosphate¹, (Sn-v-p)², Sn^{IV}-molybdoarsenate³, Sn^{IV}-tungstoarsenate^{3,4} and hydrous antimony sulphide⁵. The present report summarises the synthesis, characterisation and ion-exchange behaviour of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate (Sn-W-P).

Experimental

Tin(IV) chloride pentahydrate (Poland) and phosphotungstic acid (U.S.A.) were used. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

A Elico LI-10 pH meter, a Bausch & Lomb Spectronic-20 colorimeter, and a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer were used for potentiometric, spectrophotometric and ir absorption measurements. The shaking was performed in a SICO temperature controlled shaker.

Synthesis of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate (Sn-W-P): Sn(IV) tungstophosphate was prepared by adding 0.1 M tin(IV) chloride solution to 0.1 M tungstophosphoric acid (PWA) solution in different volume ratios (Table 1). The mixture was heated to boiling

and then adjusted to the desired pH value. The resulting precipitate was allowed to stand for 24 h at room temperature. It was filtered and washed with 1 M HCl followed by demineralised water (dmw). The gel was dried at 40°. The dried product was broken down into small granules by immersing it in water. These granules were dried, and were subjected to refluxing in 6 M H₃PO₄ for 100 h. The resulting material was washed with dmw and converted into the H⁺-form by treatment with 1 M HNO₃ in the usual manner.

Ion-exchange capacity: The ion-exchange capacity of various samples of Sn-W-P was determined by the usual column method (Table 1).

Chemical composition: The exchanger (200 mg) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid mixture (2 : 1). Tungsten was determined with α -benzoin oxime gravimetrically as tungsten(VI) oxide⁶. In the filtrate Sn^{IV} was reduced with lead, and then determined by the potassium dichromate method⁶. Phosphate was determined by the ammonium molybdate method⁶. The mole ratio of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate was found to be 2 : 1 : 3.2 (Sn-W-P).

Chemical dissolution: A sample (100 mg) of the exchanger was taken in a flask with the solution (50 ml) concerned. After shaking for 6 h, the undissolved portion of the exchanger was filtered off. Tin, tungsten and phosphorus were determined spectrophotometrically in the filtrate. The results are given in Table 2.

pH-titrations: pH titrations were carried out by the method of Topp and Pepper⁷. The results are plotted in Fig. 1.

Heat treatment: Sample S_A was heated at different temperatures in muffle furnace for 1 h. The ion-exchange capacity of the heated samples was determined. The effect of temperature upon ion-exchange capacity is shown in Fig. 2.

Measurement of ir spectra: Ir spectra of samples (S_A and S_B) of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate and of phosphotungstic acid in H⁺-form dried at 40°, were taken by the KBr disc technique. The results are presented in Fig. 3 and Table 3.

Distribution coefficient determination: The distribution coefficient (K_d) for metal ions was determined on Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate (sample S_A) in different solutions. The cation-exchange loading for the system was less than 3% of the apparent ion-exchange capacity. The following equation was used for calculation,

$$K_d = \frac{I-F}{F} \times \frac{50}{0.50}$$

where, I is the volume of EDTA solution (5 mM) used to titrate the original cation solution, F is the volume of EDTA solution (5 mM) used to titrate the cation solution after equilibrium.

The total solution was 50 ml and the amount of exchanger 0.50 g. The results are given in Table 4.

Column operation: For separation studies, a column (30 × 0.3 cm dia) was used, and exchanger (0.50 g) was kept in the column with glass wool support. The rate of flow was 9 to 10 drops min⁻¹. The effluent was titrated with EDTA solution (5 mM). Quantitative separations of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and of Hg^{II}-Cu^{II} were achieved on these columns.

Results and Discussion

The various samples of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate have been prepared at different pH values. It is clear from Table 1 that at pH 3 it shows ion-exchange capacity as well as mechanical stability. The synthesised samples A and B show the same ion exchange-capacity and same apparent stability. The unrefluxed (UR) samples show less ion-exchange capacity than the refluxed one. The refluxing of the material in 6 M phosphoric acid solution for 100 h increases the ion-exchange capacity. It hints to the possibility that the refluxing develops some new additional exchange sites in the molecule of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate.

A comparative study of stannic tungstophosphate with tungstoarsenate (Sn-W-As) and molybdoarsenate (Sn-Mo-As) (Table 2) shows that the material under study is more stable than the tungstoarsenate and molybdoarsenate. It has been reported earlier

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF SYNTHESIS AND ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF Sn^{IV}-TUNGSTO-PHOSPHATE

Reagent: 0.1 M Stannic chloride + 0.1 M tungstophosphoric acid

Sl. no.	pH of mixture	Mixing ratio	I.E.C. for Na ⁺ (meq/g)		Remarks
			UR	R	
1.	0	2:1	0	—	Unstable
2.	1	2:1	1.04	0	
3.	3	2:1 (S _A)	1.61	1.22	Stable
4.	3	2:1 (S _B)	0.66	1.20	Stable

S_A = Stannic tungsto phosphate prepared by using phosphotungstic acid synthesised in the laboratory. S_B = Stannic tungsto phosphate prepared by using imported phosphotungstic acid. UR = Unrefluxed sample. R = Refluxed sample.

that almost all the inorganic ion-exchangers get dissolved in alkaline medium completely but tin(IV)-tungstophosphate exhibits significant chemical stability in 10⁻³ M NaOH solution. It gets dissolved negligibly in 0.1 M NaOH. Thus, this ion-exchange material possess salient features for performance studies in alkaline medium.

The pH-titration curves (Fig. 1) show the mono-functional characteristics of the samples and their ion-exchange capacity to be 2.50 meq g⁻¹, while its apparent ion-exchange capacity is 1.20 meq g⁻¹. It means that the apparent ion-exchange capacity is only about 48% of the calculated one.

The ion-exchange capacity of Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate decreases on drying in air with increase in temperature. It is quite stable upto 500°. The curves (Fig. 2) indicate that all the three materials can be used as ion-exchanger upto 600°. The order of their thermal stabilities regarding the loss in ion-exchange capacity upon drying is as follows: tungstoarsenate > tungstophosphate > molybdoarsenate.

The ir spectra (Table 3) reveal that the absorption maxima at 3 500-3 100 and 1 700-1 600 cm⁻¹ are mainly common in all the three spectra, which means that the designated constituents and their mode of presence is common. The maxima at 1 200-900 cm⁻¹ is shown by the samples S_A and S_B while PWA absorbs at 1 080 cm⁻¹, but these two peaks correspond to the same designation. The shift in band frequency may be due to difference in the crystal structures of these two materials, i.e. stannic tungstophosphate and phosphotungstic acid. In the lower frequency range, ir radiations are absorbed by PWA only. The designations to these peaks are given in Table 3. The ir study hints that stannic tungstophosphate and phosphotungstic acid are quite different from each other regarding their structures.

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL DISSOLUTION (mg/50 ml) OF STANNIC TUNGSTOPHOSPHATE, TUNGSTOARSENATE AND MOLYBDOARSENATE

Sl. no.	Solvent	Sn-W-P			Sn-W-As			Sn-Mo-As		
		Sn	W	P	Sn	W	As	Sn	Mo	As
1.	Water	0.0	0.0	0.02	0.65	1.0	1.8	0.0	6.6	3.8
2.	4 M HNO ₃	1.12	0.0	0.0	8.0	0.6	1.0	3.6	20.0	17.5
3.	0.1 M NH ₄ NO ₃	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.63	2.0	1.6	*	*	*
4.	0.1 M NaOH	2.8	7.5	0.3	*	*	*	*	*	*
5.	0.01 M NaOH	0.9	0.5	0.4	*	*	*	*	*	*
6.	n-Butanol	-	0.0	0.01	0.09	0.0	0.18	0.0	0.0	0.0

* Dissolve completely.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves of stannic tungstophosphate : (---) S_A and (●) S_B.

Fig. 2. Effect of heating upon ion-exchange capacity (IEC) : (x) Sn-W-P, (—) Sn-W-As and (O) Sn-Mo-As.

Fig. 3. IR spectra : (---) stannic tungstophosphate, (—) Sn-W-P and (...) phosphotungstic acid.

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRA OF STANNIC TUNGSTOPHOSPHATE SAMPLES (S_A AND S_B) AND PHOSPHOTUNGSTIC ACID (PWA)

ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	Peak appeared in	Designation
3 500-3 100 br	S _A , S _B , PWA	ν_1 (OH)
2 420 s	PWA	δ_1 (H ₂ O) coord.
1 700-1 600 m	S _A , S _B , PWA	δ_2 (H ₂ O) _t
1 200-1 900 br	S _A , S _B , PWA	δ_3 (M-OH), (H ₂ O) _{int} and ν_1 (P-O)
1 080	PWA	Superposition of ν_2 (P-O), (W-O) and aqua wagging twist and rock
1 000-975 s	PWA	Interatomic ν_4 (O-P-O)
900-880 s	PWA	
850-750 m	PWA	
570 s	PWA	
520 s	PWA	
390-360 m	PWA	Interatomic ν_4 (O-W-O)
320 s	PWA	

Our experience shows that absorption of an ion is different upon different ion-exchangers. It reveals the selectivity of inorganic ion-exchangers. The uptake sequence (Table 4) for some bivalent metal ions on Sn^{IV}-tungstophosphate at different pH values is given below.

pH 1 : Ni > Hg > Co > Cu > Mg > Sr > Ba > Ca = Zn = Cd = Mn

pH 3 : Co > Ni > Hg > Ca > Ba > Mg > Sr > Zn > Cd > Mn > Cu

pH 11 : Sr > Ba > Zn > Ca > Co > Cu > Hg > Mn > Ni > Mg > Cd

It is clear from Table 4 that there is a large difference in the K_a values of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Hg^{II}. The quantitative separations of Zn^{II} from Cd^{II}, and Cu^{II} from Hg^{II} were successively

TABLE 4— K_d VALUES (ml g^{-1}) OF METAL(II) IONS ON Sn^{IV} -TUNGSTOPHOSPHATE SAMPLE DRIED AT 40°

Ion	pH 1 (0.1 M HNO_3)	pH 3 (0.001 M HNO_3)	pH 11 (0.001 M NaOH)
Mg	57	936	672
Ca	0	3 787	3 413
Sr	9	844	21 625
Ba	3	1 590	20 000
Zn	0	755	3 520
Cd	0	580	13
Mn	0	500	750
Cu	181	280	1 750
Hg	3 250	5 850	827
Ni	7 206	7 536	730
Co	208	13500	2500

achieved on a small column of Sn^{IV} -tungstophosphate. The least adsorbed Cd^{II} was eluted with

1 mM NaOH, Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} were eluted with 0.1 M HNO_3 , and Hg^{II} was eluted with 1.5 M HNO_3 in 0.5 M NH_4NO_3 solution.

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